

HISTORY OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT

Abstract:

This article discusses the stages of development of the tourism industry. Details are given that it was done in 4 stages. The stages of development of the tourism industry are related to the factors.

Key words:

tourism, travel, tourist resources, public travel, modern tourism, tourist services

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There are several views on the history of tourism development. Scientists distinguish different stages of tourism. V.B. Saprunova, I. V. Zorin There are four stages, V.P. Gritskevich, J.R. Walker - five. Different criteria are taken as division criteria: social preconditions, technical and economic, invention of new vehicles, travel motives. It should be noted that there is currently a stereotype in the educational literature of the periodicity of the history of tourism development, which consists of four stages:

Stage 1 is the historical history of tourism. The beginning of this phase dates back to ancient times. In ancient times, the main reasons for traveling were trade, education, pilgrimage, treatment. Ancient Greek scholars and explorers of other lands traveled long distances to explore new territories (Herodotus - fifth century BC, Pythagoras - fourth century BC). At this stage, road construction was of great importance for the development of tourism. In the Roman Empire, state hotels appeared, located in cities and on main roads, a day's distance from each other on horseback. There were travel guides for travelers. With the establishment of absolutism in Europe, travel regained its popularity and became safer.

As a result, fashion began to emerge for them: in England, the "great tour" became a mandatory item of the aristocracy's educational program, which had to pass it before entering the field of professional or political activity. The route started in London, stopped in Paris for a long time and led to France and then to Italy. The way back was through Switzerland, Germany, the Netherlands. It was in the 17th and 18th centuries that the term tourism emerged in England. From the end of the 16th century, people began to travel not only for commercial but also for educational purposes.

In 1624, E. Khabarov began a series of expeditions to explore Siberia.

Peter I played a very important role in the development of Russian travel, he sent people not only on business trips, but also to get acquainted with the world around them: "look, see and write." Peter became the founder of balneological tourism. The first resort was named "Martial Waters" by the god of war and the iron Mars. He was one of the first rulers to put a lot of effort into improving transportation and roads - he was the founder of the Navy in Russia.

In the 18th century, travel became an important part of the life of a secular society. For the aristocracy, visiting Europe and the East was a privilege.

Travel was seen as a means of taking a person out of daily life, broadening their worldview, and mastering language. It has become mandatory to send children to Europe both for education and for learning life. Thus, in the Middle Ages, the goals of walking and traveling changed over time: by the middle of the 19th century, in Europe and Russia, they had commercial, educational, medical, and religious purposes. But it was too early to talk about the tourism economy, because the tourists organized their own "excursions", there was no dependence on any service providers, there was no one who thought of making a profit. There were no owners of tourist resources (one of the conditions for the emergence of the market was not met), more precisely, the resources were used for these purposes, but not used. Although some elements of modern tourism have already emerged: the construction of roads, guest houses, recreation areas; creation of transport management institutions, etc. This was a preparatory stage of tourism development.

1-picture. The first public tour organized by Thomas Cook

Phase 2 - elite tourism (early 19th century - early 20th century). In the nineteenth century, travel became more convenient: the steam engine appeared, then the first orange "Prince of Orange" (1816), the first steam locomotive (1825). In 1835 the total length of the world's railways was 2,500 km. The most important role was the revolutionary changes in the development of transport, along with the expansion of the transport network. Maritime transport is booming due to the large influx of immigrants from the ancient world to America; In the mid-19th century, large shipping companies emerged.

Scientific and technological progress and the social struggle of the working people, along with the ever-increasing prosperity of society, have led to a gradual reduction in working hours in favor of leisure. Guaranteed unpaid and subsequently paid leave was introduced (for example, in Germany, leave was first established by the Civil Servants Act of 1873). This has led to a significant increase in the flow of tourists around the world, along with improved quality and speed of transport. Accordingly, enterprises specializing in serving temporary visitors began to emerge. The modest boarding houses and "guest rooms" in the monasteries were replaced by the first hotels. In 1812, the Rigi-Klesteli Hotel was opened in Switzerland. In Germany, in 1801. The first-class Badische Hof Hotel in Baden-Baden has opened. The first mineral water resorts appeared there in the early 18-19 centuries. Since the second half of the 19th century, the leisure industry has been expanding its manufacturing sector: the hotel industry has been joined by the first travel firms with consumer travel to consumers. The first example of a comprehensive service is an 1841 vacation trip by an Englishman to a group by Thomas Cook. Services include a twenty-mile train ride, tea and buns on the train, a choir orchestra, and a city tour. The whole trip, which was attended by 570 people, cost 1 cylinder for each of them. Interestingly, Cook was pursuing social goals, not commercial ones. He made such an effort to draw attention to new opportunities for leisure use and to find new supporters for the union he led. The idea didn't materialize in one way or another, and over the next 20 years, many new travel agencies emerged in the UK. From 1862 the first catalogs of tourist trips appeared - the process of expanding tourist demand began. Thus, Thomas Cook became the founder of many attributes of modern tourism: travel agencies, reservations in transportation and hotels, travelers' checks, schedules, and travel with comprehensive information. Stage 3 is the beginning of social tourism. World War I, the economic downturn of the 1930s, and World War II had a negative impact on tourism development. At the same time, it was during this period that the most prosperous elements of mass tourism emerged in the decades after the war.

In Switzerland, for example, there is Hotelplan, which is now one of the largest manufacturers of tourism services in the country. The foundation of the company in 1935 was based on the ideas of its founder G. Duttweiler that attracting the "little man" to tourism would be an invaluable aid to the hotel industry. Mass cheap tourist trips are becoming the firm's main product. In its first fiscal year, the company sold more than 50,000 travel packages.

Stage 4 - mass tourism. Tourism was widespread during this period. From luxury, it has become a necessity for the majority of the population of developed countries. The leisure and entertainment industry is being formed with its own facilities, products, production cycle, production organization and management methods. In Western European countries, tourism companies, hotels, attractions and entertainment enterprises are being actively created during this period. In the 1950s, European tourism was mainly focused on American tourists and was a source of dollar income. The rapid growth of both outbound and inbound tourism in the 1960s and mid-1970s, as well as the increase in the number of tourism enterprises and the volume of their production. The most important indicator of the completion of the formation of mass tourism is the intensity of tourism in a particular country. The intensity of tourism indicates which part of the country's population organizes at least one tourist trip each year and is calculated as a percentage of the total population of the country or part of it over the age of 14 years. When the intensity of tourism exceeds 50%, then we can talk about the mass tourism formed.

In general, in the first half of the fourth period of tourism development, there was a wide increase in the number of leisure, tourism enterprises and the volume of services they provide. Since the 1980s, on the one hand, mass conveyor tourism (as V. Saprunova calls it) has become a mass stratified tourism, which is due to the diversity of needs and motivations of tourists, ie the proliferation of highly specialized segments. tourist demand, diversity of services offered, clear specialization of tourist services 12. Among other things, the parties began to influence the development of mass tourism with new factors - the quality of services, the economic situation of the environment and even the political situation. In the last stage of the fourth period of tourism development, there was a transition from the producer market to the consumer market of services, which requires flexibility to meet the needs of the elite and middle class.

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